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Searches for SUSY particles (electroweakinos, top squarks and sleptons) from CMS

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Abstract

A wide variety of searches for Supersymmetry (SUSY) have been performed by experiments at the Large Hadron Collider. This paper focuses on searches for electroweak production of SUSY particles as well as in compressed mass spectra. The results are obtained from the proton-proton collision data collected with the CMS detector corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 138 fb^{-1} at the center of mass energy of 13 TeV during the LHC Run 2.

1 Introduction

The Standard Model (SM) is a theory of fundamental particles of matter and their interactions. Despite being a successful theory, the SM is unable to explain the existence of dark matter (DM), matter-antimatter asymmetry, mass hierarchy problem, etc. Supersymmetry (SUSY) [1] is one of several models that can address these issues and provide a DM candidate. The analyses presented in the paper are based on proton-proton (pp) collision dataset with an integrated luminosity of 138 fb^{-1} at a center-of-mass energy of 13 TeV, collected by the Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) detector [2] at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) [3] during Run 2.

The LHC predominantly produces strongly interacting particles such as quark-gluon and gluon-gluon compared to electroweak particles. Due to their colored nature, gluino production prevails, followed by squarks and anti-squarks production. In contrast, electroweakino production processes are several orders of magnitude smaller than gluinos and squarks production, however low production cross section of these processes makes them more intriguing with larger data sets. In R-parity conserving scenarios, SUSY particles are produced in pairs, and their decay chains end with the lightest supersymmetric particle (LSP), which can escape as an undetected particle. Event signatures are marked by the presence of leptons, missing transverse momentum ($p_{\text{T}}^{\text{miss}}$), and the occurrence of hadronic activity, such as jets.

The forthcoming sections offer a concise overview of three distinctive analyses: search for top squarks in the four-body decay mode with single lepton final states [4]; search for supersymmetry in final states with disappearing tracks [5]; and combined search for electroweak production of winos, binos, higgsinos, and sleptons [6].

2 Search for top squarks in the four-body decay mode with single lepton final states

In the presence of broken symmetry, the scalar partners of SM fermion gain masses distinct from their SM partner, resulting in a mass difference between scalar states that's proportional to the corresponding mass of SM fermion. Since the top quark is the heaviest fermion in the SM, this discrepancy between its chiral supersymmetric partners could be the most significant among all supersymmetric quarks (squarks). Within this context, the lighter supersymmetric scalar partner of the top quark, known as the top squark (\tilde{t}_1), may potentially be the least massive squark. If SUSY holds true in the natural world, observations from cosmology suggest that in many models, mass of the lightest top squark should closely match that of the LSP. In this particular scenario, where the mass of \tilde{t}_1 is smaller than that of the W boson, the mass difference between \tilde{t}_1 and $\tilde{\chi}_1^0$ may be insufficient to allow for two- or three-body decays of \tilde{t}_1 . Additionally, the two-body decay of \tilde{t}_1 might be suppressed depending on specific model parameters. This motivates the investigation of decays involving $b\tilde{\chi}_1^0$, where “b” represents the bottom quark. Consequently, attention is directed towards exploring the four-body decay $\tilde{t}_1 \rightarrow b\bar{f}\tilde{f}'\tilde{\chi}_1^0$, with the fermions f and \tilde{f}' indicating either quarks or leptons.

2.1 Analysis overview

This analysis focuses on scenario where the fermions f and \tilde{f}' correspond to a charged lepton and its associated neutrino, signifying the decay products of a single \tilde{t}_1 , while two quarks emerge from the decay of the other top squark. Thus the final state consists of at least one jet, a significant $p_{\text{T}}^{\text{miss}}$, and exactly one charged lepton, which can either be an electron or a muon. Selecting final states in which one of the top squarks decays into a lepton is motivated by the reduction in the influence of multijet background contributions and increases in the efficiency of the selection process for the other top squark, which undergoes a hadronic decay. The identified jet, associated with initial-state radiation (ISR) from a parton, is required to have high transverse momentum

($p_T > 110\text{GeV}$). To suppress the SM multijet background, the azimuthal angle between the directions of the leading and the subleading jet should be less than 2.5 radians, for the events with at least two jets. The presence of neutralinos and the neutrino leads to a high p_T^{miss} ($> 280\text{GeV}$). The selection of single lepton (electron or muon) reduces the dilepton topology of the $t\bar{t}$ background. The electron and muons are selected with $p_T > 5.0$ and 3.5GeV , respectively. To reduce the contribution from W +jets background, a threshold of $H_T > 200\text{GeV}$ is introduced, where H_T quantifies the scalar sum of p_T for all jets in the event.

The strategy for signal selection is based on a multivariate analysis (MVA) followed by a counting experiment. This methodology is adapted for different $\Delta m (= m(\tilde{t}_1) - m(\tilde{\chi}_1^0))$ kinematic regions, thereby extending the scope of search across the $(m(\tilde{t}_1), m(\tilde{\chi}_1^0))$ parameter space. In instances of pair production of top squarks ($\tilde{t}_1\tilde{t}_1$), simulated samples are generated for mass ranges of $250 < m(\tilde{t}_1) < 800\text{GeV}$, incremented in intervals of 25GeV , and $10 < \Delta m < 80\text{GeV}$, incremented in steps of 10GeV . The parameter space is subdivided into eight Δm regions, ranging from 10 to 80GeV in increments of 10. For each of these Δm regions, a distinct Boosted Decision Tree (BDT) is trained.

The W +jets and $t\bar{t}$ are the main background processes. Both of these processes involve a promptly produced lepton. Additionally, there are events where the lepton originates from either the decay of heavy-flavor quarks or from misidentified hadrons that satisfy the lepton selection criteria. The latter is categorized as the non-prompt background. The non-prompt background primarily arises from $Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$ +jets processes, with a lesser contribution from W +jets and $t\bar{t}$ processes, where a jet is mistakenly identified as a lepton. The non-prompt background is estimated using a technique known as the ‘‘tight-to-loose’’ method. To estimate the contributions from prompt sources such as W +jets and $t\bar{t}$ processes, a method relying on the number of observed background events in dedicated Control Regions (CRs) within the data is employed. Background contributions originating from other SM processes, such as single top quark production, diboson processes, Drell-Yan (DY) events, etc. are estimated using simulation.

2.2 Results

Figure 1 illustrates the observed and expected numbers of signal and background events from 2017 and 2018 data analysis, across the eight distinct Δm values. A good agreement between the data and predicted background events is observed across all Signal Regions (SRs). Utilizing a 95% confidence level (CL), upper limits are determined on the masses of $\tilde{t}_1\tilde{t}_1$, presented in Fig. 1 (right). The search rules out top squark masses up to 480 and 700GeV at $\Delta m = 10$ and 80GeV , respectively. These findings constitute some of the most stringent constraints to date on the cross-section for top squark pair production, specifically focusing on the four-body decay mode.

Figure 1: The observed and expected number of signal and background events in the eight SRs for the 2017 (left) and 2018 (middle). Right: The 95% CL upper limits on the \tilde{t}_1 masses.

3 Search for supersymmetry in final states with disappearing tracks

Long-lived or semi-stable charginos associated with pure wino or higgsino DM gives a unique experimental signature known as a “disappearing track” (DTk). In $\tilde{\chi}_1^\pm \rightarrow \tilde{\chi}_1^0 \pi^\pm$ decays, the resulting pion typically carries a momentum of only a few hundred MeV. Consequently, its momentum is often too low for effective reconstruction. Meanwhile, the $\tilde{\chi}_1^0$ in these decays evades detection and retains the majority of its momentum. The chargino, on the other hand, is reconstructed as a track, encompassing hits up to the point of decay, beyond which no further hits are registered. This phenomenon leads to the DTk signature, characterized by a reconstructed track originating from the collision area along the beam trajectory and abruptly terminating within the tracking volume. Recent searches have harnessed this DTk signature to establish some of the most rigorous limits to date on chargino masses for specific scenarios. This is particularly relevant for higgsino or wino LSP scenarios involving minimal neutralino mixing.

3.1 Analysis Overview

This analysis presents an exploration into long-lived charginos, investigating a comprehensive array of final states within the framework of the R-parity conserving Minimal Supersymmetric Standard Model (MSSM). The search encompasses distinct final states categorized into 1-muon, 1-electron, and 0-lepton channels, with varying jet and b-tagged jet multiplicities, strategically employed to target both strong and electroweak production modes separately. For interpretation purposes, several simplified model scenarios featuring long-lived charginos are employed, inspired by the phenomenological Minimal Supersymmetric Standard Model (pMSSM). One of these models revolves around gluino pair production, where the gluino’s decay modes include $\tilde{g} \rightarrow b\bar{b}\tilde{\chi}_1^0$ (25%), $\tilde{g} \rightarrow t\bar{t}\tilde{\chi}_1^0$ (25%), $\tilde{g} \rightarrow b\bar{t}\tilde{\chi}_1^+$ (25%), and $\tilde{g} \rightarrow t\bar{b}\tilde{\chi}_1^-$ (25%) with associated probabilities (T5btbtLL). Another scenario involves top squark pair production, where the \tilde{t} decays as $\tilde{t} \rightarrow t\tilde{\chi}_1^0$ (50%) and $\tilde{t} \rightarrow b\tilde{\chi}_1^+$ (50%) (T2btLL). A third model focuses on bottom squark pair production, with \tilde{b} decaying as $\tilde{b} \rightarrow b\tilde{\chi}_1^0$ (50%) and $\tilde{b} \rightarrow t\tilde{\chi}_1^+$ (50%) (T2tbLL). The study accounts for varying proper decay lengths ($c\tau$) of the chargino, with a focus on benchmark models featuring $c\tau$ values of 10 cm (representing pure higgsino and wino-like states) and 200 cm (for longer lifetimes). The analysis also assesses sensitivity to the direct production of nearly pure higgsino DM candidates, considering specific topologies denoted as TChiWZ, TChiWW, and TChiW.

The DTk signatures are categorized into two groups: short tracks and long tracks. Short tracks have hits recorded exclusively in the pixel detector, while long tracks extend to include hits in both the pixel and strip detectors. The p_T of track must surpass 25 (40)GeV for short (long) tracks. When there is only one DTk candidate ($N_{\text{DTk}} = 1$), the search is conducted in hadronic DTk, muon+DTk, and electron+DTk channels. An additional channel with $N_{\text{DTk}} \geq 2$ is also explored. For the hadronic DTk channel, a requirement of hard $p_T^{\text{miss}} > 150\text{GeV}$ is imposed. In the muon+DTk and electron+DTk channels, a transverse mass criterion (m_T) $> 110\text{GeV}$ and an invariant mass condition $m_{\text{DTk},\ell} > 120\text{GeV}$ are applied. Events with $N_{\text{DTk}} = 1$ are categorized into 48 SRs based on the DTk length category, the dE/dx range, the number of jets (N_{jet}) and b-tagged jets ($N_{\text{b-jet}}$), as well as the magnitude of hard p_T^{miss} . Events with $N_{\text{DTk}} \geq 2$ are pooled into a single SR, leading to a total of 49 SRs.

While disappearing track signatures are uncommon within the SM, they can occasionally emerge due to instrumental effects, either stemming from the misreconstruction of a charged particle or from coincidental alignment of hits from distinct tracks. These backgrounds are denoted as the “real-particle background” and the “fake-particle background”, respectively. The estimation of these backgrounds relies entirely on data-driven methods.

3.2 Results

In Fig. 2 (left), the results across the 49 individual SRs are shown. A good agreement is observed between data and background, indicating no evidence of new physics. A slight systematic overestimation is observed in the short track category, which is consistent with the presence of fake-track contamination within the showering background sidebands. Figure 2 (middle and right) presents the upper limits on the cross-section for T6tbLL and T6btLL models, respectively. For the T6tbLL model, bottom squarks are excluded up to a mass of 1500 GeV. Charginos and LSPs are ruled out for masses up to 850 (1150) GeV for chargino $c\tau = 10$ (200) cm. In the T6btLL model, top squarks are excluded up to 1600 GeV, and charginos and LSPs are excluded up to masses of 1050 GeV (for chargino $c\tau = 10$ cm) and 1450 GeV (for chargino $c\tau = 200$ cm). Fig. 3 (left) showcases upper limits on the cross-section for the T5btbtLL model. Gluinos are excluded up to 2300 GeV. Additionally, chargino and LSP masses are restricted to 1.5 (2) TeV for chargino $c\tau = 10$ (200) cm. Lastly, Figure 3 (right) presents constraints on a model featuring pure higgsino DM. In this case, chargino and LSP masses are excluded up to 200 GeV.

Figure 2: The observed data and SM background predictions for the 49 SRs (left). The 95% CL upper limits for the T6tbLL (middle) and T6btLL (right) models.

Figure 3: The 95% CL upper limits for the T5btbtLL (left) and higgsino (right) models.

4 Combined search for electroweak production of winos, binos, higgsinos, and sleptons

The potential SUSY signal can result in various final states due to different production and decay modes. This analysis presents a statistical combination of several searches conducted by CMS for electroweak production of SUSY particles. Each of these searches assumes that the strongly-interacting SUSY particles are too massive to be directly produced. The results of this combined search are interpreted through the simplified SUSY models. In these models, all sparticles aside from those directly involved in the specified process are treated as decoupled. In essence, their masses are exceedingly large, thereby precluding their production or influence on the decays of the particles of interest. The targeted processes encompass the production of

the lightest neutralino ($\tilde{\chi}_1^0$), the next-to-lightest neutralino ($\tilde{\chi}_2^0$), and the lightest chargino ($\tilde{\chi}_1^\pm$). Given that sleptons are significantly heavier than charginos and neutralinos, the latter particles decay alongside W, Z, or Higgs bosons. The mixing of bino, wino, and higgsino components into mass eigenstates defines the branching fractions of neutralinos to Z and Higgs bosons.

4.1 Analysis Overview

The final states that contribute to this combined search are: (i) “2/3 ℓ soft”: This search is focused on a region of the SUSY parameter space characterized by a small mass difference between the NLSP and LSP. The presence of at least one pair of low- p_T light leptons (either electrons or muons) is required, accompanied by jets and large p_T^{miss} . The p_T of lepton is required to satisfy $p_{T,\text{min}} < p_T < 30\text{GeV}$, where $p_{T,\text{min}}$ is 3.5 (5)GeV for muon (electron). (ii) “2 ℓ ”: This search requires two oppositely charged, same-flavor light leptons along with significant p_T^{miss} . The two categories are considered: “2 ℓ on-Z”, where the invariant mass of the lepton pair is consistent with their origin from a Z boson decay, and “2 ℓ non-resonant”, which requires the lepton pair mass to deviate from the Z peak region. The leading lepton is required to have $p_T > 25\text{GeV}$, while the trailing lepton needs $p_T > 20\text{GeV}$. (iii) “ $\geq 3\ell$ ”: This search selects events with either two same-sign light leptons or a minimum of three leptons, which might encompass one or more hadronically decaying tau leptons. (iv) “1 ℓ 2b”: For this search, the presence of a light lepton ($p_T > 30\text{GeV}$) originating from the decay of a W boson is required, along with two b quarks forming a candidate Higgs boson. (v) “4b”: In this search, two pairs of b quarks, either resolved or merged, are required to form candidates for Higgs bosons. Furthermore, significant p_T^{miss} is involved. (vi) “Hadr. WX”: This analysis identifies events with two wide-angle jets and p_T^{miss} .

Modifications are implemented in the definitions of SRs and CRs within the “ $\geq 3\ell$ ” analysis to eliminate any potential overlap with the event selection criteria employed in the “2/3 ℓ soft” analysis. To ensure clear separation between the analyses, $p_T > 30\text{GeV}$ is applied for the leading lepton for 3 ℓ category in “2/3 ℓ soft” analysis. Additionally, in the context of the higgsino-bino combination, steps are taken to prevent any overlap between the “Hadr. WX” and “4b” searches. To accomplish this, specific actions have been taken. The SRs and CRs related to H-tagging in the “Hadr. WX” analysis and the single b-tagging SRs and CRs within the boosted “4b” sample have been removed.

4.2 Results

No significant deviations from the SM predictions were observed in any of the initial searches. The resulting upper limits on cross sections and mass limits for neutralino-chargino production are illustrated in Fig. 4. Concerning chargino-neutralino pair production and an LSP $\tilde{\chi}_1^0$ with a mass up to 50GeV, the combined result yields an observed (expected) limit for $m_{\tilde{\chi}_1^\pm}$ around 875 (950)GeV for the WZ final state, 990 (1075)GeV for the WH final state, and 875 (1000)GeV for a mixed topology, respectively. For higgsino pair production, the anticipated mass exclusion limit ranges from approximately 600 to 950GeV, with the least stringent constraint occurring around $B(\tilde{\chi}_1^0 \rightarrow H\tilde{G}) = 0.4$. The observed limit spans approximately 750 to 1025GeV, allowing the exclusion of masses below 750GeV regardless of this branching fraction. A higgsino-bino model, assuming nearly mass-degenerate higgsino-like $\tilde{\chi}_2^0$, $\tilde{\chi}_3^0$, and $\tilde{\chi}_1^\pm$ particles decaying to a bino-like $\tilde{\chi}_1^0$ and a SM boson, is ruled out for $m_{\tilde{\chi}_1^\pm} = m_{\tilde{\chi}_2^0}$ ranging between 225 and 800GeV, given a $\tilde{\chi}_1^0$ mass below 50GeV. In general, for the models encompassed within this combined analysis, chargino masses are excluded up to 990GeV, while higgsino masses are excluded above 1000GeV. Furthermore, the results set the exclusion limit on direct slepton pair production as illustrated in Fig. 5. For scenarios where the mass difference (Δm) between the slepton ($\tilde{\ell}$) and the lightest neutralino ($\tilde{\chi}_1^0$) is 5GeV, slepton masses up to 215GeV are excluded. Collectively, the combined searches yields an observed (expected) exclusion range for the slepton mass spanning

approximately 130–700 (110–720)GeV for $m_{\tilde{\chi}_1^0} < 50\text{GeV}$.

Figure 4: The 95% confidence level (CL) upper limits for for neutralino-chargino production in the WZ topology for the full parameter space (eft) as well as the compressed region (middle), and the WH topology (right).

Figure 5: The 95% confidence level (CL) upper limits for for direct slepton pair production: the full mass plane from the combination (left), and the compressed region, obtained by the “2/3 ℓ soft” search (right).

5 Summary

This paper summarizes the recent results from CMS on electroweak and compressed mass SUSY searches. Notably, a search for top squarks decaying through a four-body mode in single-lepton final states gives the best limits on top squark pair production cross section. The study of disappearing tracks has set new, stringent limits on wino-like or higgsino-like LSPs. Combined EWKino analysis highlights the importance of diverse search approaches, encouraging further combination studies. Exploration of these searches would be continued using data collected with Run 3 phase of LHC.

References

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